

Authentic Assessment in mathematics – practical approaches

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Abstract. This four-year longitudinal study examined how authentic assessment practices can be implemented across multiple engineering mathematics courses in higher education. Traditional assessment methods often fail to accommodate diverse learners and evolving digital contexts, while practical longitudinal examples of authentic assessment in engineering mathematics remain limited. Using Participatory Action Research (PAR), the intervention emphasized student agency, reflective learning, and assessment for learning. Across 22 course iterations involving 972 students, participants engaged in workshops, video reflections, and optional final examinations. In the final cycle, AI-supported assessment was introduced to facilitate cognitive reflection during the examination process. Descriptive and inferential analyses indicated consistent grade distributions and high levels of student satisfaction across courses. The findings suggest that embedding authentic assessment throughout course structures can promote transparency, support reflective learning, and provide a stable assessment experience, while exploratory AI use can be integrated without disrupting established assessment practices.

Keywords: authentic assessment, assessment in mathematics, NPS, AI

I Introduction

Mathematics assessment is often perceived as a rigorous and formal process, typically relying on traditional pen-and-paper methods that emphasize correct answers and require justification through intermediate steps. Villarroel et al. (2018) has found that teachers are generally reluctant to alter established assessment practices, as such changes demand time, energy, and intellectual resources (Brush & Saye, 2008). This is now challenged by the presence and capability of artificial intelligence and diverse learners.

Assessments should provide opportunities for all students to demonstrate their mathematical learning and be responsive to the diversity of learners (Suurtamm et al., 2016). Borba (2021) posed the important question:

“What are the specific roles of spaces/artifacts such as the classroom, face-to-face environments made for the intense use of Internet in education, and the “online classroom”?”

The COVID-19 pandemic and the development of AI have accelerated the speed of the change in mathematics education. The diverse learners require alternative approaches - the traditional pen and paper approach may no longer be the most effective means for students to express and justify their learning. This shift is also reflected in the literature (e.g. McFeetors et al., 2021) which highlights the need to clarify and expand classroom

assessment practices. Digital documentation, when appropriately designed, can serve as a valid demonstration of knowledge, capturing necessary information, iterations, and intermediate steps.

The concept of authenticity in assessment is multifaceted, encompassing five key dimensions: the authenticity of the task; the physical context or its relation to real-world settings, particularly technological ones; the social context; the form or outcome of the assessment; and the criteria used for evaluation. These dimensions help identify critical elements for analyzing the authenticity of assessment tasks. (Ashford-Rowe et al., 2014; McArthur, 2023). Fawns et al. (2025) emphasize the lack of practical evidence regarding authentic assessment and its challenges, particularly in preparing students for the future, preventing academic dishonesty, and promoting inclusion.

Authentic assessment has been studied across various educational levels and environments (eg. Reyes-Cedeno et al., 2019; Syaifuddin, 2020; Symonds & Mott, 2024, McFeetors et al., 2021) though definitions and interpretations of authenticity vary and cyclical student involvement throughout an entire course, and across their full mathematics studies remains rare.

In this longitudinal study, students are positioned not merely as recipients of assessment but as active participants in reflective and developmental processes throughout the course. Authenticity is understood here according to the framework proposed by Ashford-Rowe et al. (2014). While the proposed approach touches on aspects of inclusion, a comprehensive exploration of inclusive practices lies beyond the scope of this work and is acknowledged as a limitation.

Gulikers et al. (2004) argue that constructive alignment between instruction, learning, and assessment is essential for achieving educational outcomes. To foster competency development, instruction and assessment must both be authentically competency-based. This study adopts the definition of assessment for learning Swaffield (2011) and applies it throughout the learning process, within the revised framework of Villarroel et al. (2018) in the spirit of authentic assessment process.

Participatory Action Research (PAR) combines critical, participatory, and action-oriented approaches to studying (Dancis et al., 2023; Wright, 2021). Wright (2021) applied this method by engaging teacher as practitioners, with students exerting an indirect influence, while Dancis et al. (2023) demonstrates three examples of inclusion undergraduate students in classroom situations.

This study investigates the long-term consistency of a revised authentic assessment framework grounded in Participatory Action Research (PAR) across multiple engineering mathematics courses. In addition, an exploratory case of AI-supported assessment is examined within this framework. Net Promoter Score (NPS) is utilized as an indicator of students' perceptions of the learning experience, while the relationship between student perceptions and academic performance is explored using statistical analyses.

II Background

The mathematical courses

The structure of the mathematics courses examined in this study is outlined as follows. To pass a course, students were required to:

- Complete a set of exercises, referred to as workshops, designed to assess individual understanding. The number and complexity of these workshops varied depending on the course and were determined at the beginning of each term. On average, students contribute to four to six workshops per semester, depending on the course.
- Produce reflection videos in which they identified their solutions, acknowledged gaps in their knowledge, and discussed their learning experiences and outcomes with peers in four person groups. These reflections could be created using digital tools or traditional pen-and-paper methods, depending on student preference. During the academic year 2024–2025, students were permitted to utilize AI as a reflective tutor in selected tasks as part of the structured reflection process.
- Receive approval from the instructor for all submitted reflection videos. A passing grade was awarded upon successful completion of these requirements. Students seeking a higher grade were given the option to take a final examination.

The courses covered a range of mathematical topics, from basic algebra to statistics and integral transforms. The aim was to explore the applicability of the present didactic approach across different courses and to evaluate student responses to the method.

In the current educational landscape, in engineering mathematics, AI can generate solutions to many foundational problems. However, the quality of AI-generated responses varies significantly. Since students are already engaging with AI tools, this presents a pedagogically opportune moment to critically compare AI outputs with validated solutions. In more advanced tasks, students are encouraged to challenge flawed or incomplete AI-generated solutions, thereby enhancing their critical thinking and reflective skills, not only in relation to AI, but also in reconsidering their own assumptions and problem-solving strategies.

Towards Authentic Assessment

The first step toward authentic assessment involves the use of randomized exercises within virtual environments. For mathematics, and other technical disciplines, the Moodle

connection to STACK and JSXGraph provide up to date tools for graphing and randomization and, therefore, individualization is becoming standard.

However, the emergence of AI has introduced new challenges. There exists a wider range of tools and applications to students to use to help, assist, or possibly, cheat, when they are solving problems and answering in the examinations. Consequently, rethinking assessment practices is necessary. In this study, the cheating was blocked by utilizing the screen recording and supervision, when AI was used in the final examination.

Throughout the twenty-two course iterations the development of assessment for learning practices was prioritized. In this study, the courses are coded: Course 1-5. Courses 1-3 had all six repetitions and courses 4 and 5 had two repetitions. In Course 5, which was the last course included in this study, the cognitive use of AI in the examination was considered in the spring term 2025. The cognitive use of AI here was understood to apply it in a way that prohibits its use in such manner to obtain direct solutions to given problems. Instead, students were asked to either reformulate the problem or to use AI in a prescribed way.

This “traditional authentic assessment” approach was employed in twenty-one of the analyzed courses. In the final 22nd course, however, the pedagogical use of AI was introduced during the final examination. This represented an exploratory extension of the existing assessment framework: students were able to participate transparently in the assessment process, while learning outcomes remained objectively measurable. The final course thus completed the authentic assessment framework and opened new avenues for applying the PAR methodology.

By incorporating AI into the final examination, the authenticity of the assessment process was deepened. Students gained greater agency in the evaluation process, and the method proved to be a functional and reliable assessment framework. This approach augments the principles of assessment for learning as defined by Swaffield (2011) related to formative assessment and demonstrates how AI can be meaningfully integrated into authentic assessment practices in mathematics education.

Framework of Authentic Assessment Process

Nieminen & Yang (2024) emphasize that the role of instructors, assessment designers, and policymakers remains central. These stakeholders are responsible for creating conditions that nurture student agencies. Promoting agency in self-assessment does not imply lowering academic standards; rather, it involves recognizing students as active participants whose contributions extend beyond skill acquisition to shaping their own learning trajectories. Transparency is also a critical measure. Students gain insight into how

professionals evaluate learning processes, particularly through the analysis of intermediate steps, which helps them assess their own progress and construct knowledge.

As Swaffield (2011) notes, students begin to understand quality and assessment criteria through exposure to pre-solved examples, marking schemes, and comparative exercises. This enables them to formulate their own success criteria and participate actively in the learning environment. Student-generated solutions and video reflections initiate teacher feedback and broader discussions on collective progress and knowledge gaps. Feedback is no longer passively received; both students and teachers are now central stakeholders in the assessment process. This method promotes reflection, participation, and knowledge construction throughout the course. Students gain genuine agency over their learning and assessment, identifying strengths and proposing improvements from both individual and shared perspectives. These practices not only enhance learning but also support the development of lifelong learning skills, which are core attributes of assessment for learning. The used framework promotes the cyclical process of problem identification and data collection and analysis in terms of students' gap identification, and action planning with the aim of generating knowledge that can be readily applied in real-world settings to improve the learning context, practices and outcomes for the next cycle of workshops

Villarroel et al. (2018) and Raymond et al. (2013) understand authenticity as a union of realism, contextualization and problematization when teaching and assessing curricular content. Realism ensures a strong connection between academic knowledge and professional practice. This original framework is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The original authenticity model for assessment by Villarroel et al. (2018).

Contextualization situates learning outcomes within meaningful scenarios, while problematization emphasizes the transferability of skills to diverse problem-solving contexts. In assessment design, which promotes learning, authenticity is recognized as a key characteristic (Villarroel et al., 2018). Authentic assessment design seeks to replicate the types of tasks and performance standards typically encountered in professional contexts.

In engineering education, mathematics has long served as a foundational discipline for developing insight and verifying solutions. Its role in shaping students' learning and future career opportunities remains significant. Success in mathematics is closely linked to the development of autonomy, problem-solving abilities, and higher-order cognitive skills such as motivation, self-regulation, and metacognition. Authentic assessment thus aims to bridge classroom learning with real-world applications (Wiggins (1993), Villarroel et al. (2018)).

While authenticity enhances relevance, engagement, and applicability, it must be embedded within a broader pedagogical framework. This includes scaffolding, support structures, opportunities for student agency, and a focus on sustainable learning (Fawns et al., 2025). The instructional and assessment framework presented in Figure 2 is a modified version of the model proposed by Villarroel et al. (2018) .

Figure 2. The revised model from Villarroel et al. (2018).

In the revised version, workplace content is replaced by curriculum content tailored to the needs of engineering mathematics. Additionally, the reflective process is integrated into the assessment framework, fostering student agency and responsibility for learning and professional development. The five-step process is iterated throughout the courses as students demonstrate their learning outcomes with workshops, typically four to six times, corresponding to the number of workshops.

The assessment process is conceptualized as a continuously evolving, cyclical system that provides timely feedback to students regarding their performance and to instructors concerning the collective understanding of key learning outcomes. This dynamic feedback loop supports both individual and group-level learning, enabling iterative refinement of both teaching and learning practices as a form of research-based teaching articulated by Jensen & Dikilitas (2025):

- it encourages the use of multiple resources beyond course materials,
- promotes inductive reasoning and knowledge discovery beyond teacher-led instruction,
- supports autonomous learning, and
- cultivates a sense of intellectual freedom

These elements are essential for developing reflective, self-directed learners with critical skills.

In this revised framework, teacher-provided feedback delivered after analyzing student reflection videos serves as a critical mechanism for guiding learning and ensuring alignment with pedagogical goals. The cyclical nature of the assessment process also enables feedback to be contextualized and didactically meaningful for instructors. As students engage with course content in a research-oriented manner, they contribute insights from their own learning contexts, effectively acting as co-investigators and sharing the professional knowledge captured during the course. This reciprocal exchange of information enhances the validity of the assessment process and supports the development of a shared understanding of learning outcomes during the course.

Following a three-level evaluation process, through steps 3- 5 students receive the minimum passing grade. The final examination, while optional, serves as a comprehensive test of individual proficiency, offering space for self-development and provides an opportunity for students to demonstrate advanced understanding and refine their skills. This completes Step 5 in the model.

Villarroel et al. (2018) note that attributes such as decision-making and collaborative work are underrepresented in the literature on authentic assessment - particularly in terms of

practical implementation. This study addresses the need for concrete approaches to demonstrate these principles in action. This is largely due to the individualized nature of traditional assessment methods

Self-reflection and video reflection as a part of assessment process

Villarroel et al. (2018), Wiggins (1993) and Torrance (1995) recall the concept of relevance in assessment. Authentic assessment should engage students in solving problems or addressing questions that hold value beyond the classroom, or that are meaningfully contextualized in everyday life (Ashford-Rowe et al., 2014). Villarroel et al. (2018) consider that authentic assessment should be accompanied by a rubric. In the present approach, however, the rubric is replaced by a structured outline of the solution process, including intermediate steps and grading criteria. This is introduced in Step 3 in the revised model.

This design aims to enhance students' ability to justify their learning, identify gaps in understanding, and foster critical thinking. In the age of AI, these skills are particularly vital. Without a transparent framework for evaluating AI-generated responses, students would lack the critical capacity to assess the validity of such solutions. When faced with complex problems, students may be inclined to rely on AI-generated answers rather than consulting traditional sources. Therefore, the structured solution skeleton serves as a necessary scaffold for developing analytical skills and maintaining academic integrity.

This approach aligns with Villarroel et al. (2018) and Wiggins (1993), who emphasize that assessment criteria should be made explicit in advance. Transparent grading structures help students monitor their progress and understand the extent to which learning outcomes have been achieved, thereby promoting self-regulation and self-directed learning. This approach requires also disciplinarity from students. Before scaffolding they are required to test their own skills and knowledge first, and after that search for help or compare their own approach to those provided by teacher or AI.

In the early stages of developing self-evaluation skills, access to pre-graded solutions is essential. These serve as reference points that help students identify and articulate gaps in their understanding. As students' evaluative judgment matures, such scaffolding becomes less necessary. This progression enhances students' sense of agency in the assessment process, as also noted by Nieminen et al. (2025), and fosters a stronger sense of competence in the subject matter. Collegial support and structured group discussions further reinforce a sense of connectedness and belonging, particularly in the initial phases of study.

As Villarroel et al. (2018) comprise, the development of evaluative judgment is driven by formative assessment. Students must be exposed to a variety of tasks with diverse performance demands and engage in processes that help them understand, judge, and improve quality. Revealing assessment criteria—such as how intermediate steps contribute to the overall solution and how each step is weighted—is a crucial component of building self-assessment capacity. Panadero & Romero (2014) have shown that making assessment criteria explicit enables students to compare their work against standardized solutions.

In their theoretical synthesis of student agency, Nieminen et al (2025) discussed what meaningful self-assessment design might look like in the digital world. They proposed that digital self-assessment could be understood

- (1) as a tool for promoting students' self-regulation.
- (2) to develop students' digital agencies; and
- (3) to provide students with more agency over their identity formation.

These dimensions offer a framework for future research and practice aimed at making self-assessment more relevant to students' digital futures. Within the context of this study, digitality is understood as the student's freedom to choose how to utilize digital tools to conduct and present their self-evaluation. This is typically done through video-recorded panel discussions, where students reflect on their learning using formats most suitable to them ranging from pen and paper approaches, presentations and animations to annotated PDF documents. This is critical in Step 4 in the revised model.

Following the group video reflection, teacher feedback plays a pivotal role in initiating assessment dialogue. This interaction supports the development of self-regulation by positioning students as active agents who use feedback to refine their understanding of quality and adjust their work accordingly. It also strengthens students' capacity for independent judgment and encourages collaborative learning. Self-appraisal and reflection are thus embedded within a process of collective knowledge construction, without compromising the rigor of learning and instruction.

This approach addresses students' immediate learning needs while simultaneously preparing them for future challenges. The central aim of self-evaluative assessment is to cultivate students' ability to assess their own performance independently—an essential skill for their professional development.

Assessment for Learning and Formative Assessment Renewed

Pedagogical innovations, like student-centeredness, constructive alignment, and active learning, have been suggested reducing problems in student learning, engagement and motivation (e.g. Freeman et al., 2014). Like demanded by Fawns et al. (2025), these principles now form part of a broader pedagogical framework aimed at developing undergraduate competencies. This framework necessitates new pedagogical perspectives and careful assessment design.

Traditionally, incorrect answers have been viewed as diagnostic tools for identifying areas in need of improvement. However, for many students, this identification process can be challenging. Villarroel et al. (2018) suggests that errors should be addressed through mechanisms of self- and peer-assessment, supported by formative feedback (Boud & Walker, 1990; Frey et. al, 2012; Wu et al., 2015) . In this pedagogical model, peer assessment is replaced by collaborative group activities. Students do not formally evaluate each other's work; instead, they participate in panel-style discussions where each member reflects on their performance in the workshop. This is followed by a group reflection session, during which students share difficulties, compare their solutions with standard or AI-generated responses, and identify personal learning gaps. This process fosters mutual support, diverse perspectives, and trust within the learning community, reinforcing both academic integrity and authentic engagement.

The concept of assessment for learning, introduced by Swaffield (2011), is a fundamental cornerstone to authentic learning. Many students are accustomed to external evaluations of their knowledge and skills, which marks the starting point for the revised authentic learning process. To foster deeper engagement, students must learn to assess their own understanding and learning progress.

Swaffield (2011) distinguishes the terms 'assessment for learning' and 'formative assessment'. Assessment for learning has several characteristics:

- Assessment for learning is concerned with the immediate and near future
- The students and the teacher are the main stakeholders and beneficiaries of assessment for learning the learning environment,
- In assessment for learning students exercise agency and autonomy,
- Assessment for learning is a learning process in itself,
- Assessment for learning is concerned with learning how to learn as well as specific learning intentions

Formative assessment

- is a purpose and some argue a function of certain assessments.
- can have a very long-time span
- can involve and be of use to other teachers, students and other people in different settings.
- maintains students as passive recipients of teachers' decisions and actions.
- provides information to guide future learning
- concentrates on curriculum objectives.

The present pedagogical approach integrates elements from both formative assessment and assessment for learning into a revised assessment framework. Within this framework, these concepts are no longer treated as separate entities; rather, they are naturally intertwined throughout the learning process, including the final examination.

Consequently, the role of students as passive recipients of assessment decisions is no longer viable. Instead, students are positioned as active participants who apply their knowledge in meaningful and changing contexts, consistent with the principles of authentic assessment (Fawns et al., 2025; Wiggins, 1993) and with the emphasis on agency and student-centered participation described by Jensen & Dikilitas (2025, p.85):

“The contribution of research-based teaching is also key to improving the process of learning, which can promote students’ critical faculties for the following four reasons: they are able to refer to multiple resources, go beyond the teacher-led course context and materials, become more inductive, discovering knowledge by transcending the potential limitations of teacher instruction, and finally, develop competence in autonomous learning and gain a sense of freedom.”

These principles informed the design of the later courses, including the exploratory integration of AI-supported assessment practices. During the first 21 courses, students actively participated in workshops, reflection activities, and the continuous refinement of course practices. However, the final examinations remained closer to traditional forms of authentic assessment, in which students had limited opportunities to influence the assessment process itself.

AI-supported Extension the Revised Framework

Table X summarizes the key characteristics of the first twenty-one courses and the exploratory twenty-second course iteration in which AI-supported final assessment was introduced.

Table 1. Characteristics of the intervention courses.

First 21 courses	22nd course
Revised authentic assessment framework	Same framework retained
Steps 3-5 implemented during coursework	Steps 3- 5 extended to final assessment
Reflection videos	Reflection videos
Group reflection	Group reflection
Assessment embedded in learning	Assessment embedded in learning
Relative traditional final examination	Final examination as an active process
Student influence during course work	Student influence extended to final examination
No AI use in the final examination	AI-supported final examinatioion

In the 22nd course, this revised framework was extended to the final examination through the introduction of a custom-made AI-supported tool (Hurme et al. (2025, 2026); Lähteenmäki et al., (2024). The tool was designed to support the formative features outlined by Swaffield (2011) while maintaining transparency and academic integrity.

Rather than using AI to provide direct solutions, students were required to engage critically with the tool and make decisions regarding their preferred solution paths. As a result, the final examination shifted from a predominantly passive assessment event towards a more active and participatory process.

In line with the principles of PAR students tested the tool before the examination, and potential issues were discussed and addressed collaboratively. This iterative process highlights the democratic nature of the PAR approach, in which students contribute not only to learning but also to the ongoing development of assessment practices. The outcomes of this exploratory AI-supported course realization are subsequently compared with those of the preceding twenty-one course iterations representing the baseline for authentic assessment practices.

III Methods

Context and Participants

This study aimed to investigate the implementation and impact of authentic assessment practices in engineering mathematics courses. It spanned a four-year period and included 22 course realizations across five distinct mathematics courses yielding nearly a thousand students (N=972). Courses 1–3 were repeated consecutively six times each, while courses 4 and 5 were conducted twice, resulting in a total of 22 iterations.

A common implicit assumption in higher education is that higher student satisfaction should coincide with better academic outcomes. The present study explores whether this assumption holds within an authentic assessment framework.

Participatory action research

Participatory Action Research (PAR) was selected as the methodological framework for this study, grounded in the epistemological traditions of constructivism and pragmatism. Constructivism views knowledge as socially constructed through practical engagement, whereas pragmatism emphasizes the utility and practice-driven nature of inquiry (Altrichter et al. 2002; Kemmis et al., 2014). This orientation was particularly relevant in the present context, where the aim was to improve assessment practices beyond traditional examination-based approaches.

Action research simultaneously investigates action and research through iterative cycles of implementation, reflection, and refinement (Altrichter et al., 2002; Dick, 2001). PAR represents a participatory form of this approach, in which the researcher acts as a change agent addressing real-world educational challenges (Best & Williams, 2024; Dickens & Watkins, 1999). Earlier experiences, emerging data, and critical reflection continuously informed subsequent cycles, enabling the assessment model to evolve in response to participants' needs.

In this study, PAR was applied within bachelor-level engineering mathematics courses through continuous cycles of implementation, reflection, and refinement. During the courses, workshops and reflection activities generated feedback that informed ongoing adjustments to teaching and assessment practices. At the end of each course iteration, students participated in university-administered feedback surveys, and the resulting data, together with course grades, guided the redesign of subsequent implementations.

As illustrated in Figure 2, students assumed an increasingly active role in the revised assessment framework, particularly in Steps 3–5, where evaluative judgement, reflection, and feedback were emphasized. Reflection videos and collaborative discussions enabled students to identify gaps in their understanding while simultaneously contributing to the development of assessment practices. The teacher's role shifted towards facilitating dialogue and supporting the co-construction of knowledge. This democratic and dialogic process reflects the core principles of PAR, in which participants contribute not only to their own learning but also to the continuous improvement of educational practice.

PAR was considered particularly appropriate because understanding emerged through action and reflection. The outcomes of student survey informed the fine-tuning of subsequent course iterations, reinforcing the cyclical, responsive, and transformative nature of the research process.

Data Collection

The participants in this longitudinal study were first- and second-year engineering students enrolled at a university of applied sciences. Because all students enrolled in the courses were included in the institutional feedback process, separate sampling procedures were not required. This ensured that all perspectives were equally represented and accessible to both practitioners and participants, supporting the democratic ethos of research design.

Each course of study implementation forms one iteration within the revised framework. In accordance with university policy, students were invited to complete a post-course survey at the end of each course. The survey included both Likert-scale items, rated from 1 to 6, where 1 indicated the lowest and 6 the highest agreement, and open-ended questions. The Likert-scale items addressed the following statements:

- During the course, I received enough feedback on the development of my skills
- I learned new things during the course
- I achieved the learning outcomes set for the course
- Teaching and guidance supported my learning
- I have been active in my own learning during the course.

In addition, students responded to two open-ended questions:

- How can the course be improved? E.g. contents, materials and teaching methods, level of difficulty, workload.
- What was good about the course? E.g. contents, materials and teaching methods, level of difficulty, workload?

To evaluate student satisfaction, the survey included the following question for calculating the Net Promoter Score (NPS):

- How likely would you recommend this course to others in your field of study?

All the data related to student satisfaction was collected through post-course surveys, administered as part of the university's standard feedback protocol. Kara et al. (2024; 2023) identify NPS (e.g. Baehre et al. (2022)), as a simple yet effective metric for capturing student experiences and recommend its use across various touchpoints in higher education. NPS scores, scaled from -100 to +100, were automatically computed based on student responses.

Data analysis

The data analysis followed a sequential mixed-methods approach, in which qualitative and quantitative analyses were conducted in a complementary manner. The open-ended responses were analyzed first to identify themes related to students' experiences and perceptions, after which quantitative analyses were used to examine patterns in NPS scores and grade distributions across the course iterations.

The open-ended responses provided qualitative data, while the Likert-scale items and NPS scores formed the basis for quantitative analysis. The NPS scores were automatically computed from the survey responses, and all courses followed the same institutional protocol, ensuring consistency across disciplines.

For the analysis of open-ended questions, the responses were read holistically. I applied in vivo coding, using the students' own words as prompts. The analysis proceeded inductively: I labeled responses with short phrases that captured the focus of each participant's claim, such as materials, pedagogical approach, didactics, study techniques, or activation. I also wrote memos with brief interpretive comments to clarify the meaning of each code. After coding the themes were identified. The process and merged themes were verified by the second author of the article.

To examine whether student experience remained consistent across courses, data from five different mathematics courses were analyzed using one-sided ANOVA. A second analytical perspective focused on whether grade distributions associated with different levels of student experience differed statistically. This question was addressed using two complementary approaches: the chi-squared test and Jensen–Shannon divergence (Menendez et al., 1997). Together, these methods provide both a statistical and a

quantitative perspective on distributional similarity. The statistical values and results were computed with Excel.

This approach enabled the integration of students' subjective experiences with distributional analyses of NPS scores and academic outcomes, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of the pedagogical model. It should be stressed the role of the NPS score as an indicator of student experience, not as a measure of learning outcomes.

Research Questions

To analyze the revised authentic approach the characteristics arising from the student surveys and course grades were selected to interpret the findings. The study was guided by the research questions:

RQ1: How do students perceive the authentic approach?

RQ2: To what extent does the Net Promoter Score reflect student success within the authentic assessment framework?

RQ3: To what extent do grade distributions remain consistent across different mathematics courses implementing the authentic assessment framework?

IV Results

The results are structured so that first the background data are presented. The first two research questions RQ1 and RQ2 are analyzed in two phases. First, the courses in which the more traditional authentic assessment was the leading pedagogical approach are evaluated first. After that, authentic assessment with exploratory AI use is examined with respect to these two research questions. Finally, the third research question is examined as a whole.

Background data

To describe the background data, the distribution of participants is first explored. The total number of students' grades given during the longitudinal study is $N = 972$. The distribution of the number of students in the courses is seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The distribution of participants.

The following Table 2 presents the original data for NPS-scores. The number of valid number of NPS realizations in each column corresponds to number of iterations of the specific course and their sum yielding up the total number of course iterations 22,

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of NPS scores across the study courses.

	Course 1	Course 2	Course 3	Course4	Course 5
Mean	66.17	57.17	65.17	66	88.5
Std. Deviation	13.92	31.72	21.63	19.8	7.78
Minimum	48	14	33	52	83
Maximum	82	100	100	80	94
Interquartile Range	19.25	37.75	10	-	-
Number of valid NPS scores (n)	6	6	6	2	2

The Table 2 summarizes the central tendency and range of NPS values observed during the longitudinal study. Courses 4 and 5 included only two NPS measurements, limiting the interpretation of distributional characteristics, and therefore these values are not included in the box-plot presented in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Visualization of descriptive statistics of Table 3.

The data consisted of six repetitions on courses 1 to 3 and two repetitions on the other two courses. For this reason, the box-plot does not include courses 4 and 5 in the box-plot visualization in Figure 4. The distribution of the average NPS scores and the corresponding boxplots in Figure 4 and illustrate the results obtained in Table 2

The lowest average in NPS score appeared in Course 2 and was approximately 57. The range in NPS score values 86 units, which is reflected with the widest confidence interval across all data.

RQ1 Baseline Authentic Assessment Cycles

Representative NPS values were selected to explore whether differences in student satisfaction were reflected in students' perceptions of the course and in the corresponding grade distributions. To facilitate comparison while avoiding additional interpretative assumptions, the selected NPS cases were consistently presented in ascending order. This approach preserves the exploratory nature of the analysis and allows observe potential patterns without imposing predefined categorizations.

Tables 3 and 4 present the results of the student survey with Likert-scale items, rated from 1 to 6, where 1 indicated the lowest and 6 the highest agreement and Figures x and y display these statistics descriptively.

Table 3. Student survey results for two selected NPS scores.

NPS = 14 (N = 49, n = 7)

Statistic	Active learning	Teaching & guidance	Learning outcomes	Learned new things	Feedback
Mean	4.29	4.86	3.14	5.14	4.29
Std. Deviation	1.50	1.07	1.46	1.07	1.25
Minimum	2	3	1	3	2
Maximum	6	6	5	6	6
Valid values	7	7	7	7	7

NPS = 52 (N = 27, n = 21)

Statistic	Active learning	Teaching & guidance	Learning outcomes	Learned new things	Feedback
Mean	4.90	5.05	5.10	5.43	5.33
Std. Deviation	1.22	1.16	0.77	1.12	0.66
Minimum	1	1	4	1	4
Maximum	6	6	6	6	6
Valid values	21	21	21	21	21

Note. Likert scale: 1 = strongly disagree, 6 = strongly agree.

Table 4. Student survey results for two selected NPS scores.

NPS = 80 (N = 17, n = 10)

Statistic	Active learning	Teaching & guidance	Learning outcomes	Learned new things	Feedback
Mean	5.70	5.70	5.60	5.70	5.70
Std. Deviation	0.67	0.48	0.52	0.67	0.48
Minimum	4	5	5	4	5
Maximum	6	6	6	6	6
Valid values	10	10	10	10	10

NPS = 94 (N = 24, n = 16)

Statistic	Active learning	Teaching & guidance	Learning outcomes	Learned new things	Feedback
Mean	5.56	5.81	5.56	5.75	5.63
Std. Deviation	0.63	0.40	0.73	0.58	0.62
Minimum	4	5	4	4	4
Maximum	6	6	6	6	6
Valid values	16	16	16	16	16

Note. Likert scale: 1 = strongly disagree, 6 = strongly agree.

Tables 3 and 4 summarize the descriptive statistics for four selected NPS levels across the study. The total number of students enrolled in each course (N) and the number of valid survey responses (n) are indicated in the table headings. Variation in response rates reflects differences in participation in the voluntary end-of-course survey.

Figures 5 and 6 show in corresponding order student responses to predetermined statements.

Figure 5. Student responses for open-ended questions for two selected NPS values.

Figure 6. Student responses for open-ended questions for two selected NPS values.

Tables 3 and 4 together with Figures 5 and 6 illustrate representative examples from the twenty-one baseline authentic assessment cycles. Despite differences in NPS levels, the response patterns remained largely consistent, indicating that the pedagogical characteristics of the framework were stable across implementations.

In addition, the student survey had two open-ended questions related to improvement of the course and issues which already were good in the course. The open-ended responses provided qualitative data that was analyzed.

Although nearly a thousand students participated in the courses, responses to the open-ended questions were limited: 157 comments addressed course improvement, and 85 focused on positive aspects. Three main codes emerged regarding suggestions for improvement. Notably, 45 students did not suggest any changes. The materials code included remarks about digital copies of exercises, missing audio in videos, and the quantity of exercises; 17 students commented on this theme. The third code concerned pedagogics. All courses included both distance and onsite learning, but seven out of fourteen students expressed a preference for all teaching interventions to occur onsite. Five students emphasized the need to enhance resources and activation for self-study and distance learning.

Regarding what was considered good in the courses, four main codes emerged. The dominant theme was the teaching method or pedagogics, mentioned by 40 students out of 87 responses. These students indicated that the new method supported their learning process. The third and fourth codes were study materials and course content, respectively. A total of 40 students noted that the study materials, clear learning objectives, and course content were well-balanced.

Although fewer students provided numerical evaluations for the Net Promoter Score (NPS), the primary reason for their specific ratings was their perception of the course content's scope. Importantly, no issues were reported regarding the student-teacher interaction method.

The following excerpts illustrate students' reflections in the post-survey:

- "The teaching technique of the teacher is unique and very effective."
- "Effective learning without overwhelming students"
- "The course was well constructed. I would not change anything."
- "The workshop method was awesome. It made me reflect, how well did I do and what was my learning level compared to the learning outcomes"
- "Workshops work well as indicators of learning. When doing the workshop, you get a little insight into how these issues have been internalized and where there is still some room for improvement. This method relieves the pain and panic from the final examination. You cannot fail the examination, so it really feels one succeeds better in the final examination.

In the initial phase, 17 codes emerged related to suggestions for course development, and 11 codes captured what students considered positive aspects of the course. Due to the open nature of the responses, it became evident that students highlighted what they perceived as educationally meaningful, noteworthy, or evaluative in their experiences. I then continued by coding students' artefacts individually, occasionally revisiting and refining codes applied to the interview data. This iterative process resembled a recursive movement between different data points.

Three main themes were discovered: perceived support and autonomy, stress and cognitive load and fairness and transparency. The theme of stress and cognitive load encompassed reported challenges related to course materials and the learning process. Fairness and transparency were particularly emphasized in students' written reflections and excerpts.

RQ2 Baseline Authentic Assessment Cycles

The second research question aimed to examine the extent to which the Net Promoter Score (NPS) can serve as an indicator of the authentic approach, and whether the use of AI influences the NPS score. An introductory analysis was conducted at the beginning of this section to provide context for the subsequent examination.

The impact of cognitive AI use in the final examination is analyzed separately. It is important to note that the structure of the courses and the assessment procedures were consistent across all cases. The only distinguishing factor in one particular case was the integration of AI, which set it apart from other courses that followed the same framework for authentic assessment. The intention was to examine whether AI-supported assessment practices could be incorporated into the authentic assessment framework without disrupting its pedagogical characteristics.

The discussion begins with the role of NPS score as an indicator, followed by an analysis of how the use of AI in the final examination may influence the NPS score.

The effect of NPS score

A selection of representative NPS scores was drawn from the full range of scores, which varied from a minimum of 14 to a maximum of 94. These results are summarized in graphical form, and descriptive statistics for the different NPS scores are presented in the following tables. Additionally, the grade distribution for the analyzed course is included to provide further context.

The table headings correspond to the statements used in the student survey. The survey questions remained consistent across all course cycles, ensuring comparability. In the subsections that follow, the format of the presented and illustrated data remains uniform to support clarity and coherence in interpretation.

Figure 7. Grade distribution for selected two NPS-values.

Figure 8. Grade distribution for selected two NPS-values

Since the grade distributions include only students who obtained a passing grade, the number of observations shown in the figures may differ from the total number of students enrolled in the course.

A visual inspection indicates that the grade distributions for passed grades vary in shape and do not consistently resemble a symmetric bell-shaped pattern. Furthermore, visual comparison of grade distributions and corresponding NPS scores across the courses revealed that even when a course had a lower NPS score, the grade distribution did not necessarily differ significantly from others.

Table 2 summarizes the descriptive statistics of NPS scores across the study courses, while Figures 2 and present representative grade distributions in Figures 7 and 8 corresponding to selected NPS levels. A visual comparison suggests that courses with lower NPS scores did not necessarily exhibit markedly different grade distributions from those with higher NPS scores. This observation indicates that NPS alone may not fully capture variation in student performance and highlights the importance of considering additional aspects of the learning experience, such as perceived fairness, clarity of objectives, and teaching practices. The statistical examination of distributional similarity is presented in relation to the third research question.

Also, the findings challenge the original assumption that higher student satisfaction should coincide with better academic outcomes. Courses with lower NPS values did not necessarily exhibit substantially different grade distributions compared with courses characterized by higher NPS scores.

Before the analysis of the exploratory AI-supported course it was verified statistically that the baseline of NPS scores remained consistent. This is reported in subsequent section of statistical analysis.

RQ1-RQ2 Exploratory AI-supported Course

To illustrate the exploratory integration of AI within the authentic assessment framework, the final course iteration is presented separately as a case example. The purpose of this example is not to establish causal effects of AI use but to demonstrate how AI-supported assessment practices can be incorporated into the broader pedagogical model. We first examine RQ 1, and consequently RQ 2.

The corresponding data from Course 5 is presented in table 5, where the AI was used cognitively in the final examination. Also, the graphical description of Table 5 is presented right below Table 5.

Table 5. Student survey results for the course of exploratory AI use.

NPS = 88 (N = 12, n = 8)

Statistic	Active learning	Teaching & guidance	Learning outcomes	Learned new things	Feedback
Mean	4.88	5.75	5.00	5.75	5.38
Std. Deviation	1.46	0.46	1.77	0.71	0.92
Minimum	2	5	1	4	4
Maximum	6	6	6	6	6
Valid values	8	8	8	8	8

Note. Likert scale: 1 = strongly disagree, 6 = strongly agree.

Figure 9. Student responses for open-ended questions in the course of exploratory AI use.

Table 5 accompanied with Figures 9 and 10 illustrate the student responses and grade distribution obtained from the exploratory AI-supported course (Course 5). The descriptive statistics indicate that students evaluated the pedagogical approach positively, particularly with respect to guidance, opportunities for learning, and feedback received during the course. Despite the integration of AI into the final examination, the corresponding grade distribution remained comparable to those observed in the baseline authentic assessment cycles.

Figure 10. Grade distribution for the course of exploratory AI use.

When compared with the preceding twenty-one authentic assessment courses, the exploratory AI-supported course did not exhibit a substantially different response profile or grade pattern. This observation suggests that the integration of AI, as implemented in this study, did not disrupt the underlying pedagogical characteristics of the revised framework. Rather, AI functioned as an extension of the existing assessment model, while preserving transparency, student agency, and academic rigor.

RQ3 Statistical Comparison Across Courses

From background data described in Table 3 the 95% confidence intervals of NPS scores are reported in Table 6.

Table 6. 95% confidence intervals of NPS scores for the background data.

	Course 1	Course 2	Course 3	Course 4	Course 5
95% CI of Mean	51.56 - 80.78	23.87 - 90.46	42.47 - 87.87	-	-
Mean \pm Std.	66.17 \pm 13.92	57.17 \pm 31.72	65.17 \pm 21.63	66 \pm 19.8	88.5 \pm 7.78

To address the third research question, whether the NPS score can serve as an indicator of the new authentic approach, data from five different mathematics courses were analyzed. The underlying assumption was that a predominance of lower grades should correspond with lower NPS scores, whereas a high concentration of top grades should be reflected in higher NPS scores.

To investigate the student experience remain constant statistically, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted across the first three courses, Courses 1 - 3. The null hypothesis stated as “There is no difference between the courses 1 – 3 with respect to NPS score” and the corresponding alternative hypothesis “There is difference between the courses 1 – 3 with respect to the NPS score”.

ANOVA results show that there is no significant difference between the first three courses and the dependent variable $F= 0.26, p= .772$ Thus, with the available data, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

The third research question explored whether there are differences in student success across different mathematics courses that implemented the novel approach. A visual comparison of grade distributions indicated strong similarities between the courses. The data showed that the distributions were nearly identical in shape, suggesting a consistent pattern of student performance.

To assess the similarity in the shape of grade distributions between two courses, two complementary methods were applied: the chi-squared test and the Jensen–Shannon divergence (JSD) (Hurme et al., 2026; Menéndez et al., 1997). The statistics were computed with Excel and programming the formulas.

A chi-squared test of independence was conducted to examine whether grade distributions differed across selected NPS levels representing the range of observed

student experiences. Because some expected frequencies were small, grade categories were collapsed into two groups (grade 1 vs. grades 2–5). The analysis indicated no statistically significant association between NPS level and grade distribution. The test yielded a chi-squared statistic of 4.72 with 3 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.194. Since the p-value exceeds the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, we cannot reject the null hypothesis which states that the distributions are the same. This suggests that the distributions do not differ significantly in a statistical sense.

Because the assumptions of the chi-squared test required collapsing adjacent grade categories, Jensen–Shannon divergence was used as a complementary measure to preserve a more nuanced comparison of the original grade distributions as it retains sensitivity to structural differences in the original distributions that may be obscured when categories are merged.

Therefore, as a complementary approach, the Jensen–Shannon divergence was calculated to quantify the shape difference between the two grade distributions with NPS scores 14 and 94. This enables a structural comparison of grade distributions associated with very different student experiences in terms of NPS score. The resulting JSD-value was 0.0629, indicating a very small divergence.

Together, these methods provide both a statistical and a quantitative perspective on distributional similarity. The chi-squared test supports the conclusion that the distributions are not significantly different, while the low JSD value confirms that they are closely aligned in shape. Which was observed also by visual inspection.

Using both methods strengthens the reliability of the analysis and provides a more nuanced understanding of the data. It is not necessary to compute JSD values for all course comparisons in this study, as the selected cases already illustrate the key finding: student success, as measured by grade distribution, remains consistent across courses regardless of variation in NPS scores across all courses.

The exploratory AI-supported course yielded an NPS score of 88, which falls within the range observed in the preceding course implementations. The associated student responses and grade distribution followed the general patterns identified in the baseline analysis.

V Limitations.

This study has several limitations. In some cases, the number of survey respondents was low, which may affect the generalizability of findings. Although the model was tested across 22 course iterations, the Net Promoter Score (NPS) is used primarily to assess pedagogical consistency rather than course success. Due to space constraints, only selected graphical elements are presented to illustrate the full range of data. Moreover, two courses, coded as Course 4 and Course 5, have both been conducted only two times. Therefore, the boxplots of these courses are omitted.

Statistical methods used, chi-squared test and Jensen–Shannon divergence, offer complementary insights into distributional similarity. However, small sample sizes challenge the validity of the chi-squared test, which assumes sufficient expected frequencies. In such cases, alternative methods like Fisher’s exact test may be more appropriate. JSD value, while it is suitable for small datasets, does not provide statistical significance and requires contextual interpretation.

In this longitudinal study, the final course iterations included introductory use of AI, but due to the small number of cases, separate analysis was not feasible. AI was used to support cognitive reflection and reduce cognitive load, but its impact on NPS was not significant. Otherwise, the structure of the instruction and learning outcomes were similar. The use of AI was done during the course to relieve cognitive load, and it had a tutoring role. Only in one course, the cognitive use of AI was tested, and this was reported separately in the results section.

A custom AI-supported tool (Hurme et al., 2026) was introduced in the final examination, but its pedagogical implications will be addressed in a forthcoming publication. Thus, its influence remains outside the scope of this study.

Nieminen (2025, p. 566) notifies, there exists possibilities to make assessment more inclusive, but large-scale implementations are rare and so far, “inclusive assessment approaches are built on the premise that assessment should and could be made more inclusive by focusing on inclusive pedagogies, design principles and policies”. this study does not explore it in depth. Future research should investigate inclusive design principles and policies to support broader implementation.

VI Discussion

This study demonstrates how authentic assessment can be implemented longitudinally within engineering mathematics through a revised framework grounded in Participatory Action Research (PAR). The findings particularly illuminate the operationalization of Steps 3–5 of the revised framework Villarroel et al. (2018), where students actively participate in evaluation, reflection, and feedback processes. While Villarroel et al. (2018) conceptualized authentic assessment as a sequence of interconnected phases, the present study illustrates how these principles can be sustained and refined across multiple course iterations over an extended period of time.

The findings further support recent discussions concerning student agency in higher education Jensen & Dikilitas (2025) who categorizes students' roles in educational inquiry, highlighting concerns regarding whether genuine collaboration and democratic participation are achieved in practice. This study addresses that concern by offering students a democratic voice in shaping and improving course content and didactical practices. Similarly, Jones et al. (2021), who emphasized the use of appreciative inquiry to involve students in enhancing both the course and their own learning processes. By positioning students as active and autonomous participants, this study supports their role in constructing knowledge within their discipline, not as formal researchers, but as learners developing inquiry skills essential for future academic and professional success.

Findings from surveys and open-ended responses suggest that high NPS scores were often accompanied by perceptions of agency, transparency, and support, challenging the assumption that grades are the primary driver of student satisfaction. The results further indicate that student satisfaction should not be interpreted as a direct proxy for academic success. Although NPS scores varied considerably across course iterations, corresponding grade distributions remained remarkably similar. These findings challenge assumptions that student experience and academic outcomes should necessarily align in predictable ways and instead supports competence-based approaches to curriculum design Nieminen (2025). Student experience appears to be shaped by factors extending beyond grades alone, including perceptions of meaningful participation within the assessment process.

The consistency observed in grade distributions across courses represents another notable finding. Despite differences in student satisfaction, there were no indications of systematic declines in academic performance. This stability appears to be a characteristic of the pedagogical approach itself and reinforces the reliability of the revised framework. In this respect, the findings extend the work of Villarroel et al. (2018) by demonstrating that authentic assessment practices can be maintained longitudinally across different mathematics courses while preserving comparable academic outcomes.

Another important finding concerns the exploratory integration of AI into the final examination. The AI-supported course did not exhibit substantially different response profiles or grade patterns compared with the preceding authentic assessment cycles. Although the limited number of AI-supported cases precludes separate statistical conclusions, the findings suggest that AI-supported practices can be incorporated into authentic assessment without disrupting established pedagogical characteristics or compromising academic integrity. Rather than attributing pedagogical benefits directly to AI, the results indicate that AI can function as an extension of an already established assessment framework.

This interpretation aligns with blinded Brown et al. (2018), who found that students' understanding of assessment practices and their opportunities for engagement played a central role in shaping satisfaction in higher education contexts. Within the present study, students reported high levels of feedback, support, and active participation regardless of variations in NPS scores, suggesting that the pedagogical structure itself contributes substantially to positive learning experiences.

Importantly, the framework embeds students in a continuous cycle of learning, assessment, and reflection rather than limiting participation to isolated assessment events. This cyclical involvement supports metacognitive development and professional growth, making authentic assessment an integral component of the learning process. The study does not claim that AI improves assessment outcomes. Instead, the findings suggest that AI-supported practices can be integrated into an established authentic assessment framework while preserving its core pedagogical principles.

The findings suggest that:

- (1) authentic assessment practices can be sustained longitudinally across different mathematics courses;
- (2) student satisfaction, as reflected by NPS, should not be interpreted as a direct proxy for academic success; and
- (3) AI-supported assessment practices can be incorporated into the revised framework without disrupting its pedagogical characteristics.

This framework invites further development, particularly regarding the enhancement of authenticity in final assessments. Although the present study was conducted in a hybrid learning context supported by virtual environments, the underlying principles may be transferable to other higher education settings.

VII Conclusions and future work

This longitudinal study introduced a revised pedagogical framework for authentic assessment in engineering mathematics, grounded in Participatory Action Research (PAR). The approach emphasized student agency, reflective learning, and assessment for learning, and was implemented across 22 course iterations. The findings suggest that authentic assessment, when embedded throughout the course structure, can support meaningful learning experiences, foster student autonomy, and maintain consistent assessment practices across diverse mathematics courses.

The exploratory integration of AI in the final examination phase demonstrated that AI-supported practices could be incorporated into an established authentic assessment framework without disrupting its pedagogical characteristics or compromising academic integrity. However, the role of AI in assessment warrants further investigation to better understand how emerging technologies can support reflective learning, transparency, and student engagement in higher education.

Future work should focus on refining final assessment practices to further align with authentic assessment principles and on developing scalable approaches for integrating AI into assessment while preserving student agency and pedagogical coherence. In addition, more inclusive assessment practices should be explored to support diverse learners and assist educators in designing meaningful and context-sensitive assessment procedures.

Future research could examine how authentic assessment frameworks continue to evolve in response to technological developments while maintaining the core principles of transparency, reflection, and active student participation.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author.

Data Availability Statement

Due to the legal of the research, supporting data is not available.

Notes on contributors

Will be added later. Removed for blind review.

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